

Advantages of using authentic materials in teaching foreign languages

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Abstract: This article deals with advantages of authentic materials in teaching foreign languages. The proposed requirements for the article. Types of authentic materials and its difference from non-authentic materials are given.

Keywords: Authentic materials, non-authentic materials, teaching process, e-learning, classroom, teacher, learner, foreign languages.

In foreign language teaching, good, well-designed textbooks provide a lot of advantages: They follow a clear structure which usually use to CEF criteria and curriculum standard, they often present an attractive format which engages students and makes learning easier, and many textbooks also supply vocabulary glossaries or grammar sections for easy reference. And yet, there are still a lot of times when teachers will want to diverge from the clear structure that a textbook provides in order to make learning even more interesting, effective and long-lasting. Using authentic language materials is a brilliant way to make the language come alive for students. Using authentic reading texts and other authentic materials can enrich the language learning experience immensely.

Firstly, There are two general approaches: Argumenting already learned language or trying out completely new topics. Supplementing curricula topics with authentic materials in teaching real-life materials in the target language can be used to

supplement structures and vocabulary which have been presented in the curricula and textbooks with the aim of achieving an enhanced, synergistic learning effect. Such materials might include articles and other literature, videos, podcasts, songs, menus, etc., which address topics that have already been covered by textbooks. A simple approach would be to simply find authentic material in the target language which discusses a topic that was covered in the textbook, but from another perspective. Let's say that the textbook covers the topic of food and restaurants, presenting food words and the grammar of ordering. On the internet, it is amazingly easy to find a wealth of material in various levels of difficulty such as restaurant menus, articles about restaurants dining, restaurant reviews. You can then use these materials in a multitude of ways. Students can perform internet searches as group work. Teach your students how to use internet search engines in the target language. Even though this might seem self-explanatory, in reality, many students are hesitant to perform searches in the target language and need a bit of guidance. Then, assign small groups the task of researching and presenting material to the rest of the class. This approach will deliver a wealth of paybacks. In the above example of food and restaurants, each group could find authentic menus, online customer reviews, photos, etc. The classic teaching method of role playing a restaurant setting with waiters and customers will be much more effective if the students themselves have researched and found the authentic materials in the target language. These approaches support students' authentic language learning and provide long-lasting benefits. In-context reinforcement of target vocabulary and grammar structures will foster efficient and long-lasting learning effects. There is an old language teachers' adage that you need to use a new vocabulary word at least seven times in order to make it part of your active vocabulary. In my own experience of learning languages, it's more like fourteen times or even twenty-one times! In any case, finding opportunities to use the newly acquired word will help it to become a reliable

companion in applying the language naturally. Regardless of how many times you may need to encounter the word, repetition in context is much more effective than rote repetition. Encourage students to search for their own authentic foreign language materials. Students will already have acquired a certain amount of confidence in a topic already discussed in the textbooks and they will be better equipped to explore further if they already have learned key vocabulary and structures. In other words, the teachers can assign students the task of finding their own materials on a particular subject. Authentic materials develop reading skills. Because students already possess basic knowledge of topics, they will be better able to develop skills of reading or listening. This creates an environment where the skill of intelligently guessing at the meaning of a word or sentence from the context can be honed. Authentic materials are a good way to review previous topics. This is also a good way to review topics already presented weeks or months before. Find an article which roughly matches a topic which has been covered in the textbook and choose a time to review when the topic is still relatively fresh. Using authentic materials on completely fresh topics to help students develop real-world language skills. This second approach entails using authentic materials to introduce students to real-world materials and to using the language in a completely natural way. This might involve presenting an article on a current event or presenting a popular song with video or audio and then studying the lyrics. Another activity might be to select a city in a country where the target language is spoken and then find out as much information as possible about it, e.g., famous sights and museums, hotels and restaurants, history, etc.

Finding authentic materials on fresh topics for all levels of language learners. Materials can be found to suit all levels, which is a great way to build confidence in real-world language use, even for beginners. Teachers can make use of language

learning news sites for French and Spanish or Chinese, which present news articles for all levels on a variety of topics. These particular sites also offer vocabulary and grammar lists, authentic language audio, vocabulary trainers as well as context questions and testing, making it more simple for teachers to present the articles. Real-world materials will awaken students' interest and build confidence. Using this approach will sharpen students' curiosity about the target language and the countries in which it is spoken. Even if the students are pure beginners, this approach will present them with their first real-world success in using the target language. It's a great confidence builder. Authentic materials can be a fun diversion. Once again, this activity delivers great opportunities for group work. Different groups can select, research and read various materials on a single subject or on entirely different subjects. Finally, they can present their work to the rest of the class and possibly initiate a discussion. Some ideas for finding authentic materials in foreign language teaching. The internet offers the greatest wealth of authentic materials. Once students have learned how to search in the target language and have discovered the best search engines to use for the countries in question, news and magazine articles in the target language. Finding suitable news articles can be most challenging for students in the beginning stages of language learning. Teach students to use news sites which are designed for children who speak the target language as native speakers. Many countries also offer more-or-less official sites for learners of the language which present authentic reading texts in a simplified language. Videos on a variety of subjects. Easy topics such as cooking or other tutorials would be suitable for beginners because they can follow the language on the video as it is being spoken. For example, try following the instructions in the target language to make, say, a paper airplane. Of course, there is also huge amount of content available for higher levels. YouTube videos tend to teach colloquial language and listening in context which are highly valuable and desirable to students. YouTube and other sites also

usually offer automated subtitling of the videos in question. As a general rule, set the subtitles to the target language if the students can manage this. it's more effective for learning.

Secondly, It is obvious that there are many important advantages of using authentic materials. One of them increase learners motivation and reflects positively on their learning process. the use of authentic materials in language teaching is supported by many researchers. They aware of the of use this type of materials as a useful means to motivate learners. In addition, authentic materials encourage learners to learn a particular language successfully, it helps to motivate learners learn the language by making them feel they are learning the real language. There is a large amount of authentic materials in our life such as newspaper, magazine articles, tv, and radiobroad cast, daily conversations, meetings, documents, films. One of the most helpful is the internet. Whereas newspapers and other materials date very quickly, the internet is continuously updated, more visually stimulating as well as interactive. Authentic materials in language teaching are classified into three categories. They are authentic listening materials, authentic visual materials, authentic text materials. Teachers provide learners with a number of aspects such as motivation, authentic cultural background and contact with the real language variety and sufficiency to learners needs. Nevertheless, in the teaching process, they maintain an innovation teaching style and they prefer that authentic materials are used at post intermediate level because at this level, students are expected to have an expansive collection and variety of vocabulary items in the classroom. So that authentic materials are recommended to be used at pre-intermediate level because they impose an overburden on both teachers and learners. They might discourage learners who are expected to lack vocabulary and structures. Teachers demand many preparations in order to suit the level and ability of learners.

The use of authentic materials may cause students to feel demotivated and frustrated since they lack many lexical items and structures used in the teaching process. The use of authentic materials is burden for instructors teaching beginning students, as they have to spend a lot of the students. This does not mean that teachers are not able to use authentic materials in lower level classes differ from post-intermediate and advanced levels. In the result of using authentic materials at the different levels, learners enjoy dealing with authentic materials since they enable them to interact with the real language and its use and they do not consider authentic situation or materials innately difficult. In addition, experiences working with authentic data have potential to engage students in a broader suite of science practices and improve critical thinking particularly in the classroom. In fact, student data literacy has been shown to improve when given opportunities to interact with authentic data. Therefore, it is crucial that instructors not overlook the context of a data set as they help students develop their data literacy abilities. In authentic experiences may fail to engage students and students are asked to explore patterns or trends without meaning. In addition, students may find results from in authentic data more difficult to interpret than those from authentic data and students' abilities to transfer new skills to novel contexts in and outside of the classroom may be reduced. In contrast, authentic data transform a typical lesson on data interpretation by providing real-world context and making connections to disciplinary content. Student report feeling an increased emotional connection to data when they are better able to recognize practical application and relevance.

Authentic learning is the technique used in education institutes of all level to help the students understand concepts by linking academic concepts with real- world scenarios. The use of e- learning is found very useful in conveying ideas with visual and vocal methods. Intergrating e-learning and authentic learning creates a new

paradigm of learning beneficial to both the teacher and students in knowledge sharing. This study deals with the significance of authentic learning in the e-learning framework. The survey is based on a set parameters to analyze the remembering and understanding outcome of participating individuals against their ages, prior experience and educational level. The results show consistency for all the factors, showing the effectiveness of e- learning tools and authentic learning methods. Authentic learning is used in education and tuition techniques to help the students in connecting what they learn in the school to the problems, issues and concepts they face in the real world. Some authentic learning activities include role-playing, project-based learning, learning by doing and problem-based learning. Authentic learning provides better learning opportunities, help in a better understanding of a complex concepts, prepares the technology and different education tools to deliver knowledge. E- learning as the use of electronic technologies for creating a link with classroom and material learned even outside of a classroom. Basis of authentic learning is on simple idea: designing an environment that is close to the real environment improving learning. Recently teaching techniques that do not follow this basic ideas are considered ineffective in education. With advancement in visualization and simulating as well as different internet applications, the implementation of authentic learning environment is encouraged, making a bridge between classroom learning and real-world.

Herrington and Oliver [3,23-43] suggested a new pedagogical term, called "authentic learning". This term is directly related to the students' real life and prepares them to face and deal with real world situations.

William Guariento and John Morley describe authentic text as: "...one 'created to fulfil some social purpose in the language community in which it was produced' With the onset of communicative movement a greater awareness of the need to

develop students' skills for the real world has meant that teachers endeavour to simulate this world in the classroom." [2,347-351]

According to Christoff Edelhoff a text can be regarded as "authentic", if it has a purpose outside the teaching of a foreign language. He further more expresses that most audiovisual media used in a foreign language teaching can be regarded as "authentic", which can facilitate and provide the opportunity for the competence of understanding, varying on real speaking situations. Learners learn to comprehend the global-situation, which then is focused on the given channels of communication to a selective communication, triggering an action after comprehension; for example go to the correct platform to catch the train. The teacher should in such situations keep in mind that whole information is scanned and skimmed appropriately and the learner should not therefore unnecessarily burdened to look for information, not related to the action that follows the comprehension on the text.[1,7-30].

In conclusion using authentic language material is a great way to design a truly interactive class. If a foreign language class is limited to the textbook format, it will eventually pan out to be safe, predictable and mundane. By introducing authentic materials into the classroom, students will develop confidence and curiosity regarding the language as well as regarding the culture of the countries in which it is spoken. Eventually, perhaps sooner than you think, your students will be performing their own searches in their free time. The language will be truly merged with their own interests.

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